

Non-performing Loans and Financial Performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria

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Abstract

The importance of non-performing loans to the financial performance necessitated this study which aimed to examine the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In the course of the study, the primary objectives of the study were to determine the effect of loan loss provisions on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, and to evaluate the effect of loans and advances on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The population of this study comprised of all the fourteen (14) listed deposit money banks under Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) for the period of 12 years from 2010 to 2021, but only 12 deposit money banks was selected as the sample of the study. The study adopted purposive sampling technique which is the deliberate choice of a researcher due to the qualities of information it possesses. Secondary data was used for the purpose of this study. Regression analysis was employed for data analysis. The results of the analysis reveal that: (i) with the result of hypothesis one; the regression estimates results revealed that non-performing loans measured by loans loss provision ratio (LLPR) has a negative and in-significant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity ($\beta = -0.463$, $p = 0.346$) (ii) for hypotheses two, regression estimates results revealed that non-performing loans measured by loan and advances ratio (LAAR) has a positive and insignificant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity ($\beta = 0.858$, $p = 0.566$). Restrictions point to the limitations that analysts experience when conducting research. When analyzing the effect of non-performing loans on financial performance, the analyst experiences some limitations in this consideration, such as limited test measurement, among others. No research was found regarding the NPLs and financial performance during the time period of 2010-2021. The study concluded that loan loss provision (LLPR) do not significantly affect the financial performance to returns on asset and equity (ROAE), while loan and advances (LAAR) do not significantly affect the financial performance to returns on asset and equity (ROAE). The study recommended that Deposit Money Banks need to regularly review their loan portfolios from time to time to enable them to spot any adverse risk in the loan portfolio, and also adhere to the CBN guidelines which can assist in mitigating NPLs.

Keywords: Loan loss provisions, Loans and advances, Financial performance

Introduction

Globally, non-performing loans are widely recognized as one of the primary underlying factors leading to financial crisis (Khaled, 2017). Studies like Hou (2007) and Visishtha (2005) have remarked on the ambidextrous instrumentality of non-performing loans as well as its capacity to

render financial institutions insolvent and ultimately upset the whole economy. Non-performing loans often result from lending to favoured individuals or sectors that are more preferred in the economy (Mitai, 2016). The primary concern of any lending institution, while giving credit, is getting back the money lent out. Arguably, non-performing loans have the potential to negatively influence the financial performance of deposit money banks, although they have other extensive implications. This is because other prospective borrowers may find it difficult, if not impossible, to utilize the opportunity of accessing a credit facility due to unavailability of the funds. This is as a result of non-performing loans which have impeded access to extendable loans. The NPLs also affect the economy of a country which explains the reason why the Central Bank of Nigeria sets guidelines for enabling financial institutions to reduce NPLs (Wangai et al., 2015). These guidelines by the CBN mandated DMBs to continually review their loan portfolios from time to time. This should be done at least once every three months, to enable DMBs to spot any adverse risk in the loan portfolio. Despite the CBN's guidelines, the level of non-performing loans continues to rise and this has been identified as a disturbing trend (Etale et al., 2016).

Non-performing loans are widely viewed as debts that are unlikely to be recovered because the chances of them getting paid back are minimal. However, an accumulation of debt as a result of increased non-performing loans in a company's balance deteriorates available funds, as well as its stock price and value. By implication, a percentage increase in non-performing loans automatically results in decrease in the lender's stock price. As a result of this, banks may initiate recovery action plan to ensure they maintain their strength and market value and forestall the danger of losing investors and the potential for more profitable outputs for future businesses (Motley, 2016).

The high incidence of non-performing loans in the balance sheet reduces the bank's profitability and thereby affects the financial performance of deposits money banks (Uwalomwa et al., 2015). According to a research by Shrivastava et al. (2018) financial performance is a measure of how well a company deploys its assets to generate revenues. This definition is used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time, and can also be used to collectively compare similar companies across the same industry and across industries. Financial performance measures are directed at reviewing the efficient and effective utilisation of resources available to a firm aiming at maximising returns of an organisation as presented in financial statements (Makokha et al., 2017).

An organisation's financial performance can suffer significantly when there is a high occurrence of non-performing loans recorded in its financial statements. In order to maintain the right proportion of bad loan in the financial statement, many DMBs have to increase their loan loss provisions, which can lead to inadequate liquidity (Ibitomi & Micah, 2021). Many deposit money banks in Nigeria today are incurring massive losses due to the setbacks of non-performing loans in their books. The possibility of a bank making losses as a result of defaults in loans by debtors often occur in the financial sector, particularly DMBs (Saliu et al., 2020). According to Samuel (2017), two members of the Central Bank of Nigeria's Monetary Policy Committee issued a statement on the bank's website indicating that four Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) had been identified as operating with excessive non-performing loans (NPLs) on their financial statements, while also falling below the required liquidity ratio of 30 percent. Furthermore, Ibitomi and Micah (2021) revealed that the banking industry experienced a liquidity shortfall of ₦2.3 trillion at the end of December 2016, compared to ₦1.93 trillion in 2015. However, the identities of the affected DMBs were not disclosed in the statement.

Ologunla and Asaolu (2020) assert that the Nigerian Deposit Money Banks are confronted with a significant challenge posed by the substantial volume of non-performing loans, which not only impedes the efficiency and expansion of the banking sector but also endangers the growth and development of Nigeria's economy. The significant amount of unpaid loans in Nigeria should not be overlooked as they can have an impact on the Nigeria's economy (Ibitomi & Micah, 2021). Meanwhile, some deposit money banks have had to increase their loan loss provision after their

unpalatable experience in relation to non-performing loans and its resultant effect on their liquidity position. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has reported that deposit money banks in Nigeria are facing a significant challenge due to the high number of non-performing loans. This is evident from the substantial increase in loan loss provisions for various banks in the first quarter of 2017. For instance, Zenith bank's loan loss provision increased by 198% to ₦42.9billion in the first quarter of 2017 from ₦14.23billion in the first quarter of 2016; Stanbic IBTC's loan loss provision increased by 65.1% from ₦8.45billion in the first quarter of 2016 to 13.95% in the first quarter of 2017; Ecobank's loan loss provision increased by 62.4% from ₦25.99billion to ₦42billion; Wema bank's provision against loan loss increased by 43.7% from ₦61million to ₦88million, among others, as reported by (Bonny & Motolani, 2017).

Another challenges faced by the Nigerian deposit money banks is the management of loaned out funds and advances which will adversely affect the financial performance of DMBs and if appropriate measures are not carried out, it could result in liquidation as in the case of Oceanic Bank Plc and Intercontinental Bank Plc (Ozurumba, 2016). A large number of studies have been conducted in relation to non-performing loans and financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria (Ojo & Somoye, 2017; Lawrence & Foluso, 2017; Daniel, 2016). Also, other scholars outside Nigeria have examined how non-performing loans influence the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks (Lucy & Julius, 2016; Muhammed & Gang, 2016; Ugoani, 2016; Ozurumba, 2016). However, little attention tends to have been paid by local authors on how loan loss provisions and loans and advances have impacted the financial performance Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Hence, this study stands to fill the gap by examining the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Research objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are:

1. To determine the effect of loan loss provisions on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
2. To evaluate the effect of loans and advances on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Research hypotheses

In line with the objectives above the following null hypotheses were formulated:

H₀₁: Loan loss provisions do not significantly affect the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Loans and advances do not significantly affect the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Literature review

Non-performing loans

The term non-performing loan has been defined differently by various scholars. In the view of a scholar like Singh et al. (2021), a non-performing loan refers to a loan where the borrower has defaulted in payment, particularly when they have failed to make scheduled payments towards both the principal (original amount) and interest. Most loans become non-performing, if payments are more than 90 days. Non-performing loans are defined as loans that have not repaid the principal and/or interest for more than 90 days after maturity, according to Kingu et al. (2018). Furthermore, Magali and Qoing (2015) explain that a non-performing loan or bad loan is one that is over 90 days late and no longer generates interest for the bank. According to Budiharya et al. (2017) also explained non-performing loan as a loan that is past due and cannot be repaid by the debtor, including the interest, within the specified contractual period. Despite this situation, financial

institutions have contingency plans in place to address it, such as setting aside funds to cover any possible losses on loans, which are referred to as loan loss provisions. These institutions also remove all uncollectible debts from their profit and loss accounts. Meanwhile, commercial banks extend loans to profit-driven companies and other entities on a daily basis.

Non-performing loans measures

The non-performing loans that were employed in the course of this study will include loan loss provision, and loans and advances. Each of these measures is discussed below:

a) Loan loss provision: The term “Loan Loss Provision” refers to the amount reserved from the profit to cover the non-performing loan (Bishnu, 2018). In reality, Loan Loss Provision is a safeguard against potential future problems that may arise from borrower defaults (Gupta, 2010). The amount set aside by banks is what is termed “loan loss provision (LLP) (Ozili, 2018). Loan loss provision is utilised by banks as a credit risk management technique to decrease the estimated loss on a bank’s loan portfolio. The provision of a cushion against loan loss becomes very important as banks' credit extension makes them susceptible to loan default as a result of deteriorating economic conditions which impacts borrowers’ ability to repay loans (Ozili & Outa, 2017). The main objective of loan loss provision has been identified to include making forecasts on banks' future loan default, reduction of taxes through managing bank earnings and capital, managing volatility of income and earnings as well as reducing fluctuations in risk-weighted asset that affects banks performance (Sonali & Amadou, 2012). One notable advantage of LLP is that even before the actual loss can be determined, LLP enables banks to estimate loss from a particular loan portfolio (Christian et al., 2014). During economic upturns, loan loss provisions should lead to direct charges against earnings, as banks anticipate future losses on their loan portfolios when the economy enters a downturn (Ahmed et al., 2012). When these anticipated loan losses eventually manifest, then banks can then take advantage of these reserves, thereby absorbing the losses without deteriorating capital (Bencharles & Nwankwo, 2021).

In conclusion, loan loss provision is an amount that a bank sets aside to cover the cost of bad loans, which may result from a customer defaulting on their loan or the need to restructure loan terms. According to Bencharles and Nwankwo (2021), the loan loss provision can be calculated by using this formula:

$$\text{Loan loss provision ratio (LLPR)} = \frac{\text{Loan loss provision (LLP)}}{\text{Average total asset (TA)}}$$

b) Loans and advances: According to Julia et al. (2021), loan refers to an agreement of lending money with interest and a plan to repay it. Categorically, loans can be classified in two perspectives: bank loans and advances versus customer loans and advances. The payments for bank loans and advances comprise short-term placements and placements with banks and discounters, which encompass balances held with other banks both inside and outside Nigeria (FBN, 2022). Customer loans and advances consist of overdrafts, term loans, staff loans, and commercial papers (CBN, 2019). According to Ajibola and Olowolaju (2017), loans and advances can be calculated by using this formula:

$$\text{Loans and advances ratio (LAR)} = \frac{\text{Loan and Advances}}{\text{Total Deposit}}$$

Financial performance

The concept of financial performance is a measure of an organization’s level of policy to achieve its desired financial goals in terms of money. According to Kariuki and Peddy (2017), business financial performance provides managers and decision-makers with an impartial and accurate means of evaluating the results of their business strategies and operations. This facilitates a measurement of a company’s overall financial health over a period of time and can be used to compare similar companies in the same industry. Similarly, Shrivastava et al. (2018) argued that financial performance is an indicator of the effectiveness with which a company employs its assets

to generate revenue. This definition is used as a general measure of a company's overall financial health over a given period of time, and can be used to collectively compare similar companies across the same industry and across industries (Eshna, 2022). Shoukat and Nadeem (2015) assert that financial performance is a relative assessment of a company's ability to utilise and profit from assets associated with its primary business.

Pinto et al. (2017), the financial performance of deposit banks plays a crucial role in economic policy making and serves as a means to evaluate the outcomes, performance, efficiency, and effectiveness of monetary policies. In essence, financial performance evaluation can be considered a relative assessment used to evaluate a company's utilization of assets linked to its primary business and capacity to generate revenue (Will et al., 2022). Abdolazim (2015) suggests that the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks can serve as a benchmark for evaluating other DMBs in the same industry, based on factors such as size, capitalisation, and workforce. DMB's financial performance indicators include Net Operating Income (NPI), Return on Equity (ROE), Earnings before Interest and Tax (EBIT), Return on Assets (ROA), Profit after Taxes (PAT) and Net Asset Value (NAV) (Hawaladar et al., 2017; Pinto et al., 2017). This study is limited to two measures of financial performance: Return on Assets and Return on Equity (ROE).

Financial Performance Measures

a) Return on assets (ROA): Onyefulu et al. (2019), return on assets (ROA) can be defined as “the ratio of net income to total assets,” and it provides insights into how efficiently a company's management is utilising its actual investment resources to generate profits. ROA is a commonly utilised metric for evaluating the efficiency and operational performance of a company, as it assesses the returns generated from the assets funded by the company (Abdel Megeid et al., 2020). Return on assets is computed by dividing the net revenue before extraordinary items and taxes by the average worth of total assets (financial and nonfinancial) over the same period and it measures the profitability of the banking sector (Albulescu, 2015). According to Albulescu (2015), return on assets can be calculated by using this formula: ROA= net operating profit/total assets.

$$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{net operating profit}}{\text{total assets}}$$

Return on assets (ROA) is a metric that provides a comprehensive analysis and demonstrates the overall profitability and performance of an entity. It is the income ratio that is directly related to its total assets, as stated by Khrawish (2011). Through comprehensively metric assessment, return on assets (ROA) assesses the ability of bank management to generate income through effective deployment of assets (Schmidt, 2023). In other words, it reveals the efficiency with which a bank's resources are utilized to generate income. Furthermore, it also indicates the effectiveness of the bank's management system in generating net income from all of the institution's resources (Khrawish, 2011). According to Akonga'a (2015), the return on assets (ROA) serves as an accurate indicator of the capital strength of the banking industry, with the specific measure depending on the industry. For instance, banks that require a significant initial investment are likely to have a lower return on assets.

b) Return on equity (ROE): Onyefulu et al. (2019) explains that return on equity (ROE) is a metric that measures a bank's profitability in relation to its book value of equity, which is the net asset minus liabilities. This ratio provides an indication of how effectively a company is using its investments to generate returns that contribute to growth. Adam (2022) defines return on equity (ROE) as a profitability ratio that evaluates a company's potential to produce a return on the investments made by its shareholders in the business. In other words, the return on equity is a measure of the profit a company generates for each unit of common stock. The return on equity is calculated to determine the return on the owner's investment. It is calculated as annual net income after tax divided by shareholders' equity as a measure of performance - therefore, a return on 1 means that every naira of common stockholders' equity generates 1 naira of net income. Prospective investors consider return on equity (ROE) as a crucial metric since it indicates how

effectively a company can utilise its funds to generate net income. ROE signifies the highest return that shareholders anticipate on their equity investments after factoring in all possible risks associated with the portfolio. Additionally, it denotes the rate at which returns are earned from equity investments in banks. This metric is calculated as the ratio of a company's net income to its total equity. According to Harvey (2011), ROE is an indicator of profitability that is computed by dividing the net income generated during the past 12 months by the common stockholder equity. This metric represents the rate of return earned by the owner's equity, as noted by Ahmed & Bashir (2013). It indicates the degree of management efficiency with respect to the utilisation of funds contributed by a bank's shareholders. As a matter of fact, ROE is a performance measure that holds promise as a dependable method and has been employed in several studies on a global scale, as demonstrated by Gadzo et al. (2019) and Ambrose (2017). In addition, ROE is viewed as a metric tool that evaluates the effectiveness of a bank's management system based on its utilisation of equity financing to finance operations and enhance the organisation (Ryan, 2022). According to Albulescu (2015), return on equity can be calculated by using this formula:

$$\text{ROE} = \frac{\text{net income}}{\text{shareholder equity}} \times 100$$

The return on equity assesses the return generated by the bank for its shareholders' investment, as noted by Adedeji and Depo-Mogaji (2017). Return on equity is the ratio of net income after taxes or total equity capital (Vishnava, 2023). The objective is to evaluate the funds invested by shareholders and the corresponding rate of return. Furthermore, it demonstrates the efficiency with which a bank's management utilizes the financial assets of its shareholders. ROE is employed specifically for comparing the performance of companies within the same industry. A ROE of 15-20% is generally considered good (Valix & Peralta, 2018).

Theoretical framework

This research work is based on the 'Financial Theory' due to its relevance to the study. Fundamentally, financial theory provides the foundation upon which our classification of borrowers is raised. As stated by Siddaiah (2009), the hedge borrower keeps a regular loan and repays both the principal and interest, while the speculative borrower retains a watch loan, which is an outstanding or unpaid loan that has been refinanced or renewed as a new loan. Therefore, the outstanding principal or interest is rolled over into a new loan as a result of being past due and unpaid within the specified 30 to 90-day period. The Ponzi borrower, on the other hand, would retain a substandard loan (Wanjala & Gachanja, 2020). That is, while principal increases, payments do not absorb the interest amount. However, the primary sources of repayment are insufficient to service the loan. The loan is past due for more than 90 days but less than 180 days. Given the nature of non-performing loan, this theory is considered the most suitable for this research work.

Empirical review

Global studies

Çollakua and Aliub (2021) examined the impact of non-performing loans on Kosovo banks' profitability over a time span of 2010 to 2019. The research employed econometric analysis to investigate the relationship between the two variables. The study's findings indicated that non-performing loans had a statistically significant impact on profitability, demonstrating that for every 1% rise in NPL, the Return on Assets (ROA) decreased by 0.19%, with all other variables kept constant.

Allen et al. (2020) studied commercial banks in Tanzania, focusing on the connection between non-performing loans and the performance of the country's commercial banks. The study utilised a thorough longitudinal research methodology by collecting macroeconomic data as well as panel data of 41 commercial banks (2006 to 2019). The three analysts examined the data using

fixed and random effect regression models and PLS-SEM. The results revealed the negative and non-significant relationship between Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Asset (ROA) and NPLR. They also observed the effect of annual GDP rate on both ROA and ROE and discovered it was negative. In their study, they discovered inflation and tried to study its relationship with ROA and ROE. However, unlike annual GDP, inflation turned out positive, having no significant impact on ROA and ROE. The exchange rate impacted ROE and ROA positively and significantly although the interest rate did not seem to negatively impact ROA and ROE. Thus, the paper recommends that bank management should enhance their credit risk management practices and also establish early prompt warning system as a means to alert the banks in case of NPL accumulation so that probable challenges may be forestalled.

Budiarto (2020) investigated how non-performing loans affect the financial performance of BPR in Central Java. The sample population consisted of 260 leaders from BPR in Central Java Province, out of which 150 BPR leaders were selected using a purposive sampling technique. Data analysis was conducted using SEM AMOS, shows the result that credit collectibility (business prospects, debtor performance, and ability to pay) have positive significant relationship with non-performing loans (NPLs). Furthermore, the study found that non-performing loans had a negative and significant impact on the financial performance of BPR.

Eddy et al. (2020) conducted an analysis on non-performing loans (NPL) and bank's performance. The result shows that NPL has a negative effect on ROA this means that management pays more attention to NPL levels compared to Net Interest Margin. This is because an increase in NPL results in a decline in bank performance. However, the study revealed that NPL BUKU 4 does not have an effect on ROA because these banks are large banks with a capital of more than IDR 30 trillion.

Bhattarai (2016), examining the determinants of non-performing loans in Nepalese commercial banks, discovered that while NPL ratio impairs ROA, the NPL ratio positively affects ROE. The study also identified other determinants that have a significant negative impact on NPL, including macroeconomic variables such as the real effective exchange rate. Additionally, the study found that the GDP growth rate did not provide significant value to the analysis.

Ebba (2016) conducted a descriptive research study on the financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia over a period of 2011-2015, specifically examining the relationship between non-performing loans (NPLs) and bank performance. The study revealed that NPLs have a significant negative impact on the performance of banks.

Mwangi (2014) conducted a study to examine the impact of nonperforming loans on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study aimed to determine how the nonperforming loans portfolio affected the profitability of the commercial banks in Kenya. All 46 commercial banks in Kenya from 2005 to 2011 were the focus of the study, and the researcher collected secondary data on two variables: Return on assets (ROA), which was the dependent variable, and NPL, which was the independent variable. The study utilised a simple linear regression model ($Y = a + bx$) to analyze the effect of nonperforming loans on the financial performance of commercial banks. The results of the study revealed that during the earlier years, there was a high amount of NPLs which resulted in a very low ROA. However, in the later years, the trend was different as ROA was higher, and NPLs were low.

Local studies

Afolabi et al. (2020) utilised the Granger causality approach to investigate the impact of credit risk variables, such as non-performing loans and loan-loss provisions, on the financial performance of microfinance banks in Nigeria. They collected secondary data from six (6) selected microfinance banks for the period 2012 to 2018 and conducted a unit root test on the data using the Augmented-Dickey Fuller and Phillip-Perron unit root test with the aid of E-VIEW 9 statistical software. The results revealed that the variables are fixed, thereby making them appropriate for the VAR model. Furthermore, the result of the Granger causality analysis demonstrated a pivotal link between the

credit risk variables and financial performance to include a unidirectional causality flow from non-performing loans to loan-loss provisions and from loan-loss provisions to returns on assets. In conclusion, the study proved that non-performing loan has a huge impact on financial performance among microfinance banks in Nigeria. Therefore, they suggest that microfinance banks should monitor their loan portfolios regularly and establish credit limits at the level of individual borrowers or counterparties, subject to their unique credit policies and risk tolerance.

Okoli et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between non-performing loans and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ten banks were selected from the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), and the data used were secondary data sourced from the banks' annual reports and the Nigerian Stock Exchange fact book, covering the period from 2009 to 2018. The data collected were analysed using correlation matrix. The results revealed that non-performing loans to total loans had a negative and insignificant impact on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria at a 5% level of significance. Therefore, the study rejected the alternative hypothesis and accepted the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the study found that liquid assets to total assets (LATA) had a significant negative effect on the performance (ROA) of deposit money banks in Nigeria at a 5% level of significance. This implies that a decrease in LATA would result in a 244% reduction in return on assets. The study concluded that the results were robust when using return on assets as an indicator to measure the level of performance.

Saliu et al. (2020) conducted a study that analysed the arguments and counterarguments in the scientific discussion regarding the implications of non-performing loans on Nigerian deposit money banks. The data used for the study was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, and a systematisation literary approach was employed for data analysis, which included Auto Regression distribution lag (ARDL) bound tests. The results showed that there is a significant long-term relationship between non-performing loans and the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study also found that an increase in the persistence of non-performing loans resulted in poor performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, and Non-Performing Loans reduced deposit money banks' return on assets.

Ugwu et al. (2020) examined the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria for the period 2015-2019. The study utilised both correlation and ex-post facto research designs and employed descriptive statistics and multiple regressions for data analysis. The study employed correlation and ex-post facto research designs. Descriptive statistics and multiple regressions were used for data analysis. Secondary data extracted from sources such as the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, and the Audited Annual Reports of the listed deposit money banks in Nigeria were used for the study. The findings revealed that substandard loans and doubtful loans had a statistically significant negative effect on return on assets, whereas lost loans had an insignificant negative influence on performance (Return on Assets).

Ajayi and Ajayi (2017) utilised panel progression analysis to examine the effects of credit risk management on the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria from 2001-2015. They also used Profit after Tax (PAT), a feature of panel progression analysis, as a proxy for assessing bank performance and also Non-Performing Loan Ratio (NPLR), Loan Loss Provision Ratio (LLPR), Loan to Total Asset Ratio (LTAR), and Cost per Loan Ratio (CPLR) to determine credit risk management. Subsequently, the study conducted fixed effect, random effect, and Hausman test on the variables. The study also exposed factors that negatively deplete or harm the profitability of the bank. These include NPLR, LLPR, and CPLR. The other factor is LTAR. It has the capacity to positively influence the performance of banks. With loans and advances in perspective, the study, therefore, concluded that the growth rates of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria relatively correspond to the growth rate of customers' non-performing loan. Also, the provisions for loan loss were slightly below the required amount of 8% by Basel Accord with high administration costs. Hence, the study concluded with recommendations for Nigerian banks which include ensuring highly

qualitative credit management systems and strictly adhering to professional banking ethics. It further added that Deposit Money Banks should maintain deposit mobilisation and effortlessly work towards reducing credit administrative costs to enhance efficiency and profitability.

Ozurumba (2016) examined the relationship between non-performing loans and the performances of specific commercial banks in Nigeria over the period of 2000-2013. The findings of the research indicated that non-performing loans have a significant influence on the banks' performance. And using the ordinary least square method and ratio analysis to examine the data collected, Ozurumba discovered that the relationship between ROA, ROE, non-performing loans, and loan loss provision is inversely proportional, while remaining positively correlated with loans and advances. Thus, it can be concluded that non-performing loans have a significantly negative impact on the performances of commercial banks.

Joseph and Okike (2015) investigated the impact of non-performing loans on firm profitability in the Nigerian Banking industry over a period of seven years (2006-2012). Data were analysed using the regression statistical tools and the result revealed that there was no correlation between non-performing loans (NPL) and Return on Asset (ROA) of Nigeria Banks. This means that the assets values of the firms are not affected by the level of NPL. The shareholders wealth maximisation is affected as the second result showed that there is a relationship between the non-performing loan (NPL) and Return on Equity (ROE) of Nigerian Bank.

Gap in the literature

This section examines the gaps discovered in the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance. Scholars outside Nigeria have examined the effect of non-performing loans on financial performance in a variety of domains, with varying findings (Çollakua & Aliub, 2021; Allen et al., 2020; Arif, 2020; Eddy et al., 2020; Bhattarai, 2016; Ebba, 2016; Mwangi, 2014). None of these studies, however, have examined how non-performing loan (with proxies such as loan loss provisions, loans and advances) affect financial performance in Deposit Money Banks.

Table 2.1: Effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance

S/N	Authors	Topic	Gaps
1.	Çollakua, B., & Aliub, M. (2021)	The impact of non-performing loans on banks' profitability.	Findings from this study reveals that Kosovo bank was selected as a case study, further research in this area is therefore recommended that further study should use Deposit Money Bank as a case study.
2.	Allen, E.M., Salvio, M., & Raphael, G. (2020)	Non-performing loans and financial performance of commercial banks.	The study is restricted to Tanzania.
3.	Arif, B. (2020)	The impact of non-performing loans towards financial performance of BPR in Central Java.	No theory was considered in the research work.
4.	Eddy, W., Remon, G., & Yogo, H. P. (2020)	Analysis of non-performing loans (NPL) on the bank's performance.	The criteria used in selecting banks in BUKU were not clearly stated.
5.	Bhattarai (2016)	The determinants of non-performing loans in Nepalese commercial banks.	Theories were not reviewed in the study.
6.	Ebba (2016)	The relationship between non-performing loans and the financial performance of the commercial banks.	The research work covered periods from 2011-2015, this is considered as a short time span.
7.	Mwangi, J. (2014)	The relationship between the level of non-performing loans and the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya.	Only covered seven year period.

Source: Literature Review (2023)

Scholars within Nigeria have also examined the effect of non-performing loans on financial performance in a variety of domains, with varying findings (Afolabi et al., 2020; Okoli et al., 2020;

Saliu et al., 2020; Ugwu et al., 2020; Ajayi & Ajayi, 2017; Ozurumba, 2016; Joseph & Okike, 2015). None of these studies, however, have examined how non-performing loan (with proxies such as loan loss provisions, loans and advances) affect financial performance in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks.

Table 2.2: Effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance

S/N	Authors	Topic	Gaps
1.	Afolabi, T. S., Obamuyi, T. M., & Egbetunde, T. (2020)	Effect of non-performing loans on microfinance banks' performance.	The study employed the use of Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Model and also conducted a unit root test on the data using the Augmented-Dickey Fuller and Phillip-Perron unit root test. The period sample is 2012-2018.
2.	Okoli, C. F., Ifurueze, M., & Nweze, A. (2020)	Non-performing loans and performance of deposits money banks in Nigeria.	The study used a sample of ten (10) commercial banks for the period 2009–2018. Further study should wider the study period to 2010-2021 and still use Deposit Money Bank as case study.
3.	Saliu, H. T., Idih, O. E., & Adewole, J. A. (2020)	The implications of non-performing loans on the Nigerian deposit money banks.	The study data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Further study should source their data from Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).
4.	Ugwu, C. C., Benedict, S., & Aikpitanyi, L. N. (2020)	An evaluation of the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks.	The study restricted its proxy of non-performing loans to substandard loans and doubtful only.
5.	Ajayi, L. B., & Ajayi, I. I. (2017)	Effects of credit risk management on performance of deposit money banks.	Theories were not reviewed.
6.	Ozurumba, B. A. (2016)	Impact of non-performing loans on the performance of selected commercial banks.	The study was limited to three (3) commercial banks (Access Bank Plc., United Bank for Africa, and Union Bank of Nigeria Plc. Further study should use listed deposit money bank under Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as a case study.
7.	Joseph, F. A., & Okike, B. M. (2015)	The impact of non-performing loans on firm profitability.	The research work covered periods from 2006-2012, this is considered as a short time span. The study also measures non-performing loan with the ratio of non-performing loan to shareholders' fund. Further study should adopt a different proxies to measure NPLs.

Source: Literature Review (2023)

Conceptual model

Figure 2.1: Researcher’s conceptual model
 Source: Researchers Study, 2023

The diagram above shows the conceptual model of the study with non-performing loans and financial performance of DMBs as the main constructs of the study. Non-performing loan is the independent variable while financial performance of DMBs is the dependent variable. Non-performing loans is measured with loan loss provisions, and loans and advances while financial performance of DMBs is measured with return on assets and equity. From the model, loan loss provisions are used as a predictor of return on assets and equity while loans and advances are used as a predictor of return on assets and equity.

Methodology

Research design

The study adopted *ex-post facto* research design. The reason for this is because the data used were secondary data that cannot easily be manipulated. The secondary data used for this study were sourced and obtained from Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), over a period of twelve years spanning 2010 to 2021.

Population of the study

The population of this study comprises of all the 14 listed Deposit Money Banks under Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) for the period of 12years from 2010 to 2021, which formed the entire population of the study.

Table 3.1: Listed DMBs under NGX

S/No.	Listed Deposit Money Banks
1	FBN Holdings (First Bank)
2	United Bank for Africa Plc
3	Guaranty Trust Holding Company (GTBank)
4	Access Holdings (Access Bank)
5	Zenith Bank Plc
6	Ecobank Transnational Incorporated
7	Fidelity Bank Plc
8	First City Monument Bank Plc
9	Union Bank of Nigeria Plc
10	Unity Bank Plc
11	Jaiz Bank
12	Wema Bank Plc
13	Sterling Bank Plc

14	Stanbic IBTC Holdings
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Source: NGX, 2023

Sample size and sample techniques

The sampling technique used to select the sample size from the listed Deposit Money Banks on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) was purposive sampling technique which is based on the researchers' judgment. In arriving at the sample size the following criteria was used;

- i. The bank should have been in operation during the study period that is 2010 through 2021.
- ii. The bank should be listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group during the study period.
- iii. The bank should not have been delisted by the Nigerian Exchange Group throughout the period of the study.

In view of the above criteria, 12 Deposit Money Banks was selected as the sample of the study as shown in the table below;

Table 3.2: Sampled size

S/No.	Listed Deposit Money Banks
1	FBN Holdings (First Bank)
2	United Bank for Africa Plc
3	Guaranty Trust Holding Company (GTBank)
4	Access Holdings (Access Bank)
5	Zenith Bank Plc
6	Ecobank Transnational Incorporated
7	Fidelity Bank Plc
8	First City Monument Bank Plc
9	Union Bank of Nigeria Plc
10	Unity Bank Plc
11	Stanbic IBTC Holdings
12	Wema Bank Plc

Source: NGX, 2023

Method of data collection

Secondary data was used for the purpose of this study. Secondary data are already analysed and published works of other authors which is related to the subject matter. The source of data was gathered from published financial reports of 12 listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) for the period 2010-2021. The adoption of secondary data in this study is justified mainly on the fact that the study is based on quantitative methodology and therefore requires quantitative data.

Method of data analysis

The regression analysis was used to evaluate the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. It reveals the degree of effect the independent variables has on the dependent variable.

Model specification

This study employs Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) as proxies for dependent variable, which measures financial performance. The independent variable – non-performing loan indicators; loan loss provisions Ratio (LLPR) and loans and advances (LAR).

Specifically, the study adopted the model of Albulescu (2015) with some modifications to suit this study.

This is shown below as thus:

$$ROA = f(LLPR, LAAR) \dots\dots\dots I$$

$$ROE = f(LLPR, LAAR) \dots\dots\dots II$$

The econometric form of the regression modified for the study is expressed as thus:

Model

$$ROAE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LLPR_{it} + \beta_2 LAAR_{it} + e_{it} \dots\dots\dots III$$

Where:

ROAE = Return on Assets and Equity

LLPR = Loan loss provisions Ratio
 LAAR = Loans and Advances Ratio
 β_0 = Constant term (intercept)
 e_{it} = Error term
 β_{1-2} = Coefficient of Independent

Description of research variable

Table 3.3: Variable measurements

S/N	Variable Acronym	Variable Name	Variable Measurement	Nature of Variable	Source
1	ROAE	Return on Assets and Equity	Net Operating Profit to Total Assets and Net Income to Shareholder Equity	Dependent Variables	Albulescu (2015)
2.	LLPR	Loan loss provisions Ratio	Loan Loss Provision Ratio to Average Total Asset	Independent Variables	Bencharles & Nwankwo (2021)
3.	LAAR	Loans and Advances Ratio	Loan and Advance to Total Deposit	Independent Variables	Ajibola & Olowolaju (2017)

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2023)

Results and discussion of findings

In order to determine the effect of non-performing loans on financial performance of DMBs measured by Return on Asset (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE)[ROAE] The study tested the effect of non-performing loans on the measurement of financial performance of DMBs using regression analysis.

Regression analysis

Table 4.1 H₀₁: Loan loss provisions do not significantly affect the return on asset and equity of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: ROAE	Coeff.	Std. Err	T-Stat	Prob
LLPR	-0.463	0.469	-0.988	0.346
R	0.298			
R ²	0.089			
Adjusted R ²	-0.002			
F. stat	0.977			

Source: Researcher’s work (2023) @Chosen Significant level of 5%

ROAE = $\beta_0 + \beta_1 LLPR_{it} + e_{it}$ Model One Restated
 ROAE = $\beta_0 - 0.463 LLPR_{it} + e_{it}$ Model One Restated

Regression equation result

Model one on Table 4.1 examined the effect of non-performing loans on financial performance to return on asset and equity (ROAE). The regression estimates results revealed that non-performing loans measured by loans loss provision ratio (LLPR) has a negative and in-significant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity ($\beta = -0.463$, $p = 0.346$). This implies that a per centum incremental change in loan loss provision ratio will lead to 46.3 percent decrease in financial performance to return on asset and equity.

The R-square of the model showed 8.9 percent, this shows the variations in financial performance (ROAE) could be attributed to independent variables put together (non-performing loans), while the remaining 91.1 percent variations in financial performance contribution to return

on asset and equity are caused by other factors not included in this model. Based on the probability of p-value of 0.346 being greater than the 5 per cent chosen significant level of the study, it shows that non-performing loans (loans loss provision ratio) has a no significant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity, thus the null hypothesis for model one which states that non-performing loans (loans loss provision ratio) do not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity was accepted by this finding.

Discussion of findings

Based on the probability of p-value of 0.346 being greater than the 5% chosen significant level of the study, it shows that non-performing loans do not significantly affect the financial performance to returns on asset and equity. This result against the study led by Hamza (2017) who discovered that non-performing loan ratio (NPLR) variables have a significant impact on return on assets (ROA) but correlates with the study conducted by Enpure and Lafuente (2012) who indicates that non-performing loans negatively affect efficiency and return on assets. The inverse of this study with the present study might be as a result of differences in period under study.

Table 4.2 H₀₂: Loans and advance do not significantly affect the returns on asset and equity of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: ROAE	Coeff.	Std. Err	T-Stat	Prob
LAAR	0.858	1.445	0.594	.566
R	0.185			
R ²	0.034			
Adjusted R ²	-0.063			
f-stat.	0.353			

Source: Researcher’s work (2023) @Chosen Significant level of 5

$ROAE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LAAR_{it} + e_{it}$ Model Two Restated

$ROAE_{it} = \beta_0 + (0.858 LAAR_{it}) + e_{it}$ Model Two Restated

Regression equation result

Model two on table 4.2 examined the effect of non-performing loans (loan and advances) on financial performance to return on asset and equity. The regression estimates results revealed that non-performing loans measured by loan and advances ratio (LAAR) has a positive and insignificant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity ($\beta = 0.858$, $p = 0.566$). This implies that a per centum incremental change in loan and advances ratio will lead to 85.8 percent increase in financial performance to return on asset and equity.

The R-square of the model showed 3.4percent, this shows the variations in financial performance to return on asset and equity could be attributed to independent variables put together (non-performing loans), while the remaining 96.6 per cent variations in financial performance contribution to return on asset and equity may be caused by other factors not included in this model. Based on the probability of p-value of 0.566 being greater than the 0.05 chosen significant level of the study, it shows that non-performing loans (loan and advances) has no significant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity, thus the null hypothesis for model two which states that non-performing loans (loan and advances) do not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity was accepted by this finding.

Discussion of findings

This result shows that loan and advances do not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity. This result corroborates a study by Bhattarai (2016) which found that the NPL ratio harms ROA whereas the NPL ratio has a positive effect on ROE but contradict the finding conducted by Ebba (2016) who examined the relationship between non-performing loans and the financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia for the year 2011-2015 and found that NPLs have a significant negative effect on banks.

Table 4.3: Summary of hypotheses testing

No	Hypothesis(Null)		Result	Decision	Effect
1	Loan loss provision does not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.	α_1	P=0.346<0.05	Accepted	No Significant
2	Loan and advances do not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.	α_2	P=0.566<0.05	Accepted	No Significant

Source: Researcher’s Study (2023)

Conclusion and recommendations

The study has examined the effect of non-performing loans on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria (between 2010 and 2021) using loan loss provision, loans and advances as the variables for independent on Return on Asset and Equity (ROAE). The study used a sample of twelve Deposit Money Banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at November 2022. From the regression analysis carried out, the study concludes that, non-performing loans measured by loans loss provision ratio (LLPR) has a negative and in-significant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity (ROAE). Based on the probability of p-value of 0.346 being greater than the 0.05 chosen significant level of the study, it shows that non-performing loans (loans loss provision ratio) do not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity (ROAE) of the Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria; while non-performing loans measured by loan and advances ratio (LAAR) has a positive and insignificant effect on financial performance to return on asset and equity (ROAE). Based on the probability of p-value of 0.566 being greater than the 0.05 chosen significant level of the study, it shows that non-performing loans (loan and advances) do not significantly affect the financial performance to return on asset and equity (ROAE) of the Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Drawing from these conclusions, it is recommended that Deposit Money Banks need to regularly review their loan portfolios from time to time to enable them to spot any adverse risk in the loan portfolio, and adhere to the CBN guidelines which can assist in mitigating NPLs. The study also suggests that, every loan granted by each of the banks has to be adequately collateralized to avoid loan losses or huge non-performing loans. While taking out loans and advances, due diligence should be done through non-performing loans of banks.

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